

First record of avifaunal communities in Sathyamangalam Wildlife Sanctuary, Tamilnadu, India

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Abstract

A total of 231 species of birds has been recorded for the first time from Sathyamangalam Forest Division, Erode district, based on the survey conducted from 21 to 22 of November 2009. The preliminary study established fairly good diversity of the birds in this forest division. The study also revealed occurrence of four species of birds considered critically endangered (White-back Vulture, Long-billed Vulture, Red-headed Vulture and Nephron Vulture), two endangered (Spot-billed Pelican and House Sparrow), one vulnerable (Lesser Kestrel) and five near threatened species (Oriental Darter, Lesser-fish Eagle, Grey-headed Fish Eagle, Malabar-pied Hornbill and Great-pied Hornbill). The study has also shown that Sathyamangalam Forest Division is a potential habitat for Gyps Vultures. The need for undertaking population studies of the rare and threatened species and landscape oriented studies to understand the effect of habitat on the diversity of avifauna is highlighted.

Introduction

The Indian subcontinent has diverse avian fauna with 1300 bird species (Grimmet *et al.* 1999). Of late there is an increased awareness to prepare checklist of birds on a wider scale, although such works are often confined to sanctuaries and forest ranges (Kannan, 1998; Mahabal, 2000). Collective checklist of birds for specific regions like lakes (Robertson and Jackson, 1992), wetland (Sivaperuman and Jayson, 2000; Ravindran, 1995), wildlife sanctuaries (Mahabal, 2000) and university campuses (Palot and Pramod, 2000; Nameer *et al.* 2000) have also been published. The present survey was undertaken at the

junction of Eastern and Western Ghats, Tamil Nadu, India to quantify the diversity of avifauna.

Sathyamangalam Forest Division is located in Erode district of Tamil Nadu. The Forest Division provides an extensive and varied wildlife habitat and this is reflected in the diversity of its bird life. Owing to the large contiguous forests and connectivity with adjoining reserve forests, it possesses wide variety of endangered species. The present study was a preliminary survey of the birds for first time in this forest division. The goal of the study was to look for the diversity of birds, assess their occurrence, understand feeding habit and habitat in the division.

Study area

Sathyamangalam Forest Division forms a part of the Nilgiri Biosphere Reserve, encompasses large contiguous reserve forests extending over 1455 km². Physiographically this landscape is considered important as it forms the meeting place of two distinct geographical regions of biodiversity, the Eastern and Western Ghats (Chandrasekaran and Kumaraguru, 2010). The lower portion of Sathyamangalam Forest Division covering an area of 524.34 km² has been declared as Sathyamangalam Wildlife Sanctuary (Fig. 1). Sathyamangalam is located between the latitudes 11° 29' to 11° 48' and longitude 76° 50' to 77° 27'. This division shares its eastern boundary with Erode Division, north-western boundary with Chamrajnagar Division and northern boundary with Bilgiri Rangan Hills. On the southern side, Nilgiri North and Coimbatore Divisions are separated by the Moyar river, which runs along the Moyar Gorge.

Another source of water to this division is from river Bhavani, which runs through Coimbatore division and enters into Sathyamangalam forests in Bhavanisagar Range. The forests around this place, comprise a diversity of vegetation ranging from dry thorn scrub to patches of semi-evergreen forests. The vegetation of the area falls into five categories as: Dry thorn forests, Dry deciduous forests, Mixed deciduous forests, Shola forests and Grasslands, Riparian-fringing forests and Deciduous forests with manipulated or plantation zone (Chandrasekaran and Kumaraguru, 2010).

The terrain is gently undulated in the Moyar valley with elevation ranging from 960m to 1266m in Bhavanisagar,

Sathyamangalam, Talavadi, Talamalai and Hasanur ranges. The slopes and plains are subjected to hot and dry climate. The average minimum and maximum temperature are 21°C and 27°C in the plateau and 26°C and 33°C in the plains. The average annual rainfall of the sanctuary over ten year period is 824mm. The bulk of rainfall is derived from the north east monsoon during the months of September, October and November. Climatically, the area has four seasons: winter (December - February); summer (March - May); south west monsoon (June - August); and north east monsoon (September - November).

Materials and methods

The present list is the outcome of bird survey carried out in Sathyamangalam forest division under the banner of Madras Naturalist's Society and Forest Department. Survey was carried out for of two days on 21st, 22nd of November 2009 with the help of several teams of volunteers. It was ensured that, each team had atleast one person who was able to identify all the birds of this region confidently. The teams were provided with data sheets, handouts about the methodology, a map of the study area and a write-up about the habitat conditions such as the forest type and altitudinal range. The area was surveyed for birds in all the major habitats.

Estimation was based on standard encounter rate method (Javed and Kaul, 2002). It was performed on the existing transects. Birds seen were identified and recorded along with feeding habit, habitat type and status (abundant, common, uncommon and rare). The birds recorded were categorized into eight trophic guilds, namely frugivores, piscivores, carnivores,

granivores, insectivores, nectarivores, omnivores and scavengers (Ali and Ripley, 1983). The checklist is based on actual sightings and has not been "smoothed" to hide the inherent randomness of the data. The doubtful entries were not taken in to account.

Results and discussion

A total of 231 species of birds have been recorded and listed in Table 1. Among the birds, based on the sightings, 13 rare species and 33 abundant species were recorded. The composition of birds in different feeding guilds in Sathyamangalam showed that the insectivorous guild was the most abundant (34% of the total species) and scavenger guild was the least abundant guild (with only 1%). The composition of other six guilds was omnivores 21 percent, piscivores 16 percent, frugivores 6 percent, granivores 6 percent, carnivores 13 percent and flower/nectar feeders 3 percent, as depicted in Fig 2. Four critically endangered Gyps vultures, endemic to India were recorded during the survey. The sustenance of these vultures was ensured by the natural deaths and the carcasses left along the valley by predators, which provide enough food for these scavengers. The rivers and reservoirs that flow through this area favour the population of piscivores and migratory birds. The following species in this study area deserve much attention owing to their conservation status.

1. White-backed Vulture (*Gyps bengalensis*) (Critically Endangered)

A bird encountered in and around civilization till three decades back. Now almost decimated due to the usage of the

veterinary drug diclofenac, ingesting the poison through dead carcasses of cattle thrown by villagers. The survey area of Sathyamangalam being a typical savannah in the low lands, holds a sizable population of this species. The continuity of the habitat with Mudumalai and Bandipur Tiger Reserves, enables perennial supply of dead animals and this being the migratory corridor of elephants, is the favoured habitat of this species. The nesting and breeding pockets are yet to be ascertained and studied in detail. The authors have sighted this species frequently in the survey area upon dead animals or soaring.

2. King or Red-headed Vulture (*Sarcogyps calvus*) (Critically Endangered)

This species was not frequently encountered in field trips, as compared to the earlier species, due to its non gregarious nature and low numbers, but nevertheless seems to be having a viable population.

3. Nephron or Egyptian Vulture (*Neophron percnopterus*) (Critically Endangered)

This was the least encountered species in the field trip. The sighting of this vulture was rare, to be precise, only on two occasions. The status and population dynamics are still a mystery, apparently seems to be the worst sufferer due the indiscriminate use of NSAIDS.

4. Long-billed Vulture (*Gyps indicus*) (Critically Endangered)

Small numbers of this species were recorded along Moyar river. Two birds

were seen at Nandipuram camp during the survey. The authors have seen this species in association with other vultures on carcasses in the wild.

**5. Bar-headed Goose (*Anser indicus*)
(Vulnerable)**

A long distance migrant, probably from Mongolia, was seen at the precincts of Bhavani-sagar dam. The latest radio-telemetry studies have established their migration from in and around Mongolia and other staging areas (Bird migration study of BNHS & FAO on Bird Flu). This is encountered every year, if earlier records of bird watchers in the study area are to be taken into confidence. This is a bird that feeds on fresh shoots of vegetation in and around the wetlands of Bhavanisagar.

**6. Great Indian or Pied Hornbill
(*Buceros bicornis*) (Vulnerable)**

A bird usually seen in the low hills of Nilgiris in and around Moyar valley, which forms a part of the study area. The authors have seen them on different occasions, specifically during the fruiting of *Ficus* species. A lateral migrant, which otherwise breeds in the higher altitudes of the Nilgiris.

**7. Amur Falcon (*Falco amurensis*)
(Least concern)**

A bird seldom seen in the low hills of the Nilgiris in and around Moyar valley, which forms a part of the study area. Old records indicate the occurrence of the species in the lower altitudes of the Nilgiris (Ali and Ripley, 1983) which has been re-established in the present survey. The distinct indicator is its red-feet, by which its name red-footed falcon has come.

However, differentiation of the female from that of kestrel is difficult. This is believed to be a migrant from Himalayas.

**8. Steppe Eagle (*Aquila nipalensis*)
(Vulnerable)**

An European migrant sighted in the Savannah forests adjoining the Moyar valley. It is another long distance migrant like the Bar-headed Goose, which is encountered every year, sporadically in the study area. The authors have seen them on carcasses along with vultures at least twice.

9. Painted Sandgrouse (*Pterocles indicus*) (Least concern)

An endemic species, partial to dry scrub land was found on the plains adjoining Moyar valley. A colourful and dainty bird often spotted squatting on the roads, only to be disturbed on close approach, adds beauty of this otherwise barren jungle in summer months. These birds congregate in pools of water, at dawn and dusk to quench their thirst and during this time, their calls are distinct and revealing. Possibly a successful breeder in this biotope, however no firm records of nesting or breeding sites were established so far. Shares a peaceful coexistence with the Great Stone Plover.

10. Great-stone Plover (*Esacus recurvirostris*) (Least concern)

A master of camouflage, this bird is usually located only at the penultimate moment of approach, when it flies away silently revealing a sudden white under the drab brown colour. During breeding time, the calls are resonant through the jungle, but otherwise a very silent bird. Seemingly,

a successful breeder in this biotope. It is often encountered during the monsoon months and shares a peaceful co-existence with the Painted Sandgrouse.

Conclusion

This is the first ornithological survey in Sathyamangalam Forest Division and it has brought out the fact that the division is a potential habitat for Gyps vultures. Further work should focus on systematic surveys for Gyps vultures in order to determine the population size of this species in the region. The present study can serve as a benchmark for avifaunal diversity of a typical forest tract such as Sathyamangalam Forest Division. Landscape oriented studies are needed to investigate the effect of habitat on the diversity of avifauna.

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